

METHODOLOGY OF CREATIVITY DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL EDUCATION

Maraimova S.Y.

1st-year master's degree student of Angren University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652363>

Abstract. *In this paper we will adhere to the definition of creativity proposed by B.G. Meshcheryakov. Creativity is the creative capabilities (abilities) of an individual that can manifest themselves in thinking, feelings, communication, individual types of activity, characterize the individual as a whole and/or its individual aspects, products of activity, the process of their creation. Currently, a number of studies are devoted to the study of the structure of creativity. J. Guilford describes six components of creativity: - the ability to detect, disclose and pose problems; - the ability to generate a large number of ideas; - the ability to respond to stimuli in a non-standard way; - the ability to modify and improve an object; - the ability to synthesize and analyze.*

Keywords: *creativity, pedagogy, modern psychological dictionary, application of innovative technologies, identification of musical creativity, primary school students, adolescence, development of creativity, self-awareness.*

According to research in the historical context, the concept of creativity has long been the subject of scientific debate. Currently, there is a tendency in scientific literature to differentiate the concept of "creativity". The traditional concept of "creativity" has a wide range of definitions. The generic component that determines creativity is activity. This position is generally accepted in domestic science, as it is the position on the dominant criterion of creativity itself and its result - novelty [11]. The study and analysis of philosophical, psychological, and pedagogical literature shows that the concept of "creativity" is quite broad and attracts researchers from a large number of branches of scientific knowledge. Initially, the problem of the phenomenon of creativity was considered from the point of view of the traditions of mythology and religion.

Creativity from the point of view of an integral property of God, creation from nothing; a certain mystification was embedded in this concept [17]. In the philosophical dictionary, the concept of "creativity" is presented as a purposeful human activity that carries a certain transformative force [13]. Studying creativity from the point of view of a philosophical category, it is necessary to turn to such a central property of human consciousness as intentionality. The etymology of the word "intentionality" means "intention". In philosophy, this category is a phenomenon that is directed at a certain object, i.e. determines the vector of some activity. If we consider creativity from the position of intentionality, then we can typologize creativity according to the principle of the direction of creative vectors as follows:

1. The interiorized type of creativity is a vector of creativity directed inside the subject of creativity (i.e. into subjective reality). The interiorized type of creativity is the creation of one's self, one's personality. The essence of this type of creativity comes down to the accumulation of energy potential in the depths of the human soul.
2. The exteriorized type of creativity is a vector of creativity directed outside the subject of creativity (i.e. from the outside into objective reality itself). Exteriorization is the rarest creative phenomenon, since in order to create something outside

oneself (i.e. in objective reality), it is necessary to have a certain energy reserve that would be sufficient for this type of activity [10, p. 108].

N.A. Berdyaev interpreted the concept of "creativity" as freedom of the individual. In his works he states: "Creativity purifies and elevates a person. Creativity is always a positive experience, the revelation of the self, a deep experience, overcoming oneself" [3, p. 106]. In psychological studies of various methodological directions, the phenomenon of creativity is studied in the most detail, interpreted from various positions. Thus, Z. Freud, the founder of psychoanalytic theory, defined creativity as one of the forms of personal activity that can arise in the process of relieving internal tension by redirecting one's energy to achieve positive, socially approved goals.

This phenomenon was called sublimation by Z. Freud [3, p. 106]. Later, in humanistic psychology, in the works of A. Maslow and K. Rogers, a different direction in studying the phenomenon of creativity appears. Humanistic psychologists describe creativity from the point of view of the ability to deeply comprehend and understand one's own experience, as self-actualization and the ability to self-express [29]. In modern psychological dictionaries, the concept of creativity is interpreted in a broad and narrow sense of the word. "Creativity is a type of human activity that generates something qualitatively new. Something that has never existed before and has socio-historical value." In a broad sense: "Creativity is any practical or theoretical human activity in which new (at least for the subject of the activity) results (knowledge, solutions, methods of action, material products) arise" [4, p. 649].

In psychology, following philosophical interpretations, the phenomenon of creativity is considered from two points of view: from the point of view of the psychological process of creating something new, and also from the point of view of the totality of personality traits that ensure its involvement in this process" [61, p. 331]. R. Sternberg wrote that creativity requires the presence of six specific but interconnected sources, which he includes: intellectual abilities, knowledge, personal qualities, motivation, environment, types of thinking [53]. According to V.I. Kolesnikova, creativity is inextricably linked with the intellectual abilities of individuals. It includes three components of intellectual abilities: 1. The synthetic ability to see problems in a new light and avoid the usual way of thinking; 2. Analytical ability to evaluate the effectiveness of ideas; 3. Practical-contextual ability to convince others of the value of an idea [9].

E.P. Ilyin, continuing the line of studying the phenomenon of creativity, focuses on the psychological mechanisms of creativity, formulating the definition of this concept as follows: creativity is "spiritual activity, the result of which is the creation of original values, the establishment of new, previously unknown facts, properties and patterns of the material world and spiritual culture" [7, p. 10]. According to E.P. Ilyin, creativity and the creative process function as a single, integral system, and the following components are distinguished as its main characteristics: the dominance of unconscious components of the psyche, spontaneity, unpredictability of the result, autonomy, efficiency, symbolism of manifestations, relativization of opposites, a wide time range (from compression in an instant to the expansion and differentiation of various stages) [7].

S.A. Novoselov gives a definition of the creative abilities of an individual at the intersection of pedagogy and psychology, indicating that creative abilities are "a synthesis of properties and individual psychological abilities of an individual, which are subjective conditions for the successful implementation of a certain type of creative activity. "Creative abilities are not limited

to the knowledge, skills and abilities that an individual possesses. They are revealed in the frequency of an individual's perception and awareness of a new type of situation, in the quantity and clarity of the formation of creative tasks, in the speed and effectiveness of finding and mastering new methods of activity, in the level of novelty and social significance of the creative result obtained" [27, p. 11].

From a pedagogical point of view, creativity is one of the types of human activity, which is an integral process due to a number of specific features inherent to it, namely: □ the presence of a contradiction, a problem situation or a creative task; □ social, personal significance, progressiveness; □ the presence of objective (social, material) prerequisites, conditions for creativity; □ the presence of subjective prerequisites for creativity (personal qualities, knowledge, skills, especially positive motivation, creative abilities); □ novelty and originality of the process or result [2].

Creativity is carried out through activity, is realized in activity and integrates activity into its structure. But also, the creative process correlates with the process of activity according to a number of structural features (needs, motives, actions, etc.), which makes it possible to distinguish between both processes. The description of these processes is optimal according to the features of "similarity – difference" [10]. One of the most recent concepts of creativity accepted by teachers is the so-called "investment theory". This concept was developed by R. Sternberg and D. Lavert, they claimed that "... creativity requires independence of thinking from stereotypes and external influence. A creative person independently poses problems and solves them autonomously" [7].

Creativity is one of the fundamental characteristics of personality. V.I. Andreev described the typology of creative personality, and also included five fundamental characteristics (personality types) in it [14]: 1. Theoretician-logician is a type of creative personality, characterized by the ability to make logical broad generalizations, to classify and systematize information. People of this type are able to clearly plan their creative work, widely use already known methods of scientific research. This type of creative personality is characterized by a high level of awareness and erudition. Based on already known theoretical data and concepts, they develop them further. Everything they start, they bring to a logical conclusion, supporting their justifications with references to numerous primary sources;

2. The intuitive theorist is characterized by a highly developed ability to generate new, original ideas, people of this type of creative abilities are major inventors, creators of new scientific concepts, schools and trends; 3. Practitioner (experimenter) - this type always strives to test their new original hypotheses experimentally. People of this type love and know how to work with activities; 4. The organizer as a type of creative personality has a high level of development of the ability to organize other people, a team for the development and implementation of new ideas. Under the leadership of this type of people, innovative scientific schools and creative teams are created. People of the organizational type are distinguished by high energy potential, sociability, the ability to subordinate other people to their will and direct them to solve large creative problems; 5. The initiator is characterized by initiative, energy, especially at the initial stages of solving new creative problems. But, as a rule, the initiator quickly cools down or switches to solving other creative problems. Thus, creativity is one of the necessary conditions for the development of personality, which includes creative activity, leading to the emergence of new ideas, products and discovering something new in the subject himself and existing forms of culture.

This process is impossible without the participation of the cognitive abilities of the individual, his motivational and value spheres. According to Yu. L. Sirotkin, the English-language analogue of the concept of creativity is the concept of "creativity". This concept is considered in the works of scientists - both teachers and psychologists. At the everyday level, creativity manifests itself as ingenuity - the ability to achieve a goal, find a way out of a seemingly hopeless situation using the environment, objects and circumstances in a non-standard way. More broadly - a non-trivial and witty solution to a problem [19].

The concept of creativity was first used by D. Simpson in 1922 to define a person's ability to abandon standard, stereotypical ways of thinking. But creativity has been actively studied by psychologists since the second half of the 20th century. Currently, there are many different points of view on the concept of "creativity". And, in this regard, there are a number of definitions of this concept. All this is due to the insufficient study of this phenomenon. This concept was proposed by J. Guilford and E. Torrance in 1950. Initially, creativity was considered by the authors from the point of view of a universal cognitive ability of a person, as the ability to create something new. In psychology, creativity is understood as the ability to generate unusual ideas, deviate from ordinary patterns of thinking, and quickly find solutions to problematic situations. [15]. According to R. Sternberg, creativity involves the ability to take reasonable risks, be willing to overcome obstacles, find internal motivation, be tolerant of uncertainty, and be willing to confront the opinions of others. He also believed that creativity is impossible to manifest without a creative environment [5].

Many educational researchers, referring to the characteristics of creativity, describe it in terms of creative ability, the manifestation and development of which is associated with the development of imagination and fantasy. Psychologists also claim that the development of creativity can qualitatively change a person's personality. D. B. Bogoyavlenskaya presents the phenomenon of creativity in her works as follows: "creativity is the ability not only to perform any activity at the highest level, but to transform and develop it." The author also defines creativity as a deep personal quality that is expressed in an original formulation of a problem filled with personal meaning. Particularly emphasized is the fact that creativity is a general feature of the personality and affects creative productivity regardless of the sphere of manifestation of personal activity [16]. S.M. Shurukht understands creativity as "the process of overcoming inertia in thinking, feelings, and communication. A creative person is always more tolerant of others: he is ready to accept that his usual way of behaving may not be the best, but he has accepted it precisely because of habit; and also that each person lives in his own world and sees this world in his own way, independently, and not in the way that those around him impose on him" [20, p. 87]. L.D. Lebedeva points out that creativity (in a broad sense) must be considered as an independent phenomenon, the manifestations of which are available for observation in the process of human creativity, the result (product of the creative process), and the characteristics (properties) of the individual as an attribute of the creative personality type [12].

V.A. Slastenin considers creativity as an ability that is capable of reflecting the deep properties of individuals, creating original values, and making non-standard decisions. The author refers to this concept in connection with the characteristics of modern approaches to education, since one of the fundamental requirements today is the development of a creative personality that would be able to go beyond the known, make non-standard decisions, and create products characterized by their novelty [8]. Creativity is one of the conditions for creative self-development

of a person's personality, and is also a significant reserve for its self-actualization. It manifests itself as receptivity, sensitivity to problems, openness to new ideas and a tendency to destroy or change established stereotypes in order to establish something new, to obtain non-trivial, unexpected and unusual solutions to life's problems [9]. At present, we can talk about the established tradition of understanding creativity as an ability that reflects the deep property of individuals to create original values, make non-standard decisions, and go beyond the known; as an integral property of a person that embodies his or her creative potential [2].

In the concept of L.D. Lebedeva and N.V. Bibikova, creativity is described from the point of view of a holistic phenomenon and is considered: as the process itself; as a result of the creative process; as a characteristic of the creative personality type [12]. Within the framework of this approach, the structure of creativity includes the following components: - creative orientation of the personality; □ productive thinking; □ special abilities [13].

J. Guilford and E. Torrance described the following criteria of creativity [15]: - fluency (ease, productivity). This criterion represents the speed of creative thinking, which is measured by the total number of correct answers to a specific question or answer options when thinking; - flexibility. The criterion is characterized by the ability to quickly switch and is determined by the number of groups of these answers; - originality. The criterion reflects the originality of creative thinking, the originality of the approach to the problem; is determined by the number of rare answers, the originality of the answer structure; - accuracy. The criterion is an indicator of the harmony, logic of creative thinking, the adequacy of the goal; - risk propensity. The criterion demonstrates the ability to use unusual materials, colors, images, ways of solving a problem, possibly not characteristic of this problem. When studying the phenomenon of creativity, the authors considered and described various models of the structure of creativity.

Thus, T.A. Barysheva and Yu.A. Zhigalov developed a theoretical model of the structure of creativity as a systemic (multi-level and multidimensional) mental formation, which they imagine as follows. In their opinion, creativity includes seven symptom complexes: motivational, emotional, intellectual, aesthetic, existential, communicative, competence. Each of these symptom complexes is a subsystem of creativity and includes a number of psychological parameters (subelements) [18].

D. Feldman proposed a model of the creative process consisting of three complementary parts. It includes three interconnected components, which include: □ reflection: is the main process that distinguishes humans from animals, allowing for the formation of self-awareness, self-esteem, and the use of language to plan, reflect, and analyze the world; - purposefulness or intentionality: a process that allows for the organization of the experience "inside and outside the organism", together with faith in the possibility of change for the better, allows for real changes in the environment; - mastery of transformation and reorganization methods: processes that are offered by culture and determine individual differences in processes and phenomena [18].

In the process of developing creativity, pedagogical efforts can be aimed at developing certain qualities of a creative personality: leadership, unconventional thinking, determination, persistence, conscious free discipline, independence of thinking and judgment, ability to cooperate in a group[6]. The criteria for identifying creativity are discussed in the works of various authors. On the one hand, we find similar positions, and on the other, the authors identify the features of creativity. According to E.E. Tunik, the main qualities of a creative personality include: curiosity, imagination, complexity, and a tendency to risk[18].

According to T.Yu. Khabarova, creativity of primary school students is considered from the point of view of the individual's ability to organize and implement creative activities in a non-standard way with setting new goals, using elements of originality in the methods of their implementation, as well as a new distribution of roles and updating of existing experience of participation in individual and collective creativity [19]. An original approach to identifying the criteria of creativity is offered by E.E. Podguzova, who identifies two aspects that reveal the concept of "creativity": cognitive and personal. The cognitive aspect reveals creativity in comparison with the level of human intelligence. Since this phenomenon is a problem of the relationship between the creation of something new and the acquisition and application of already developed knowledge and established skills. Accordingly, creativity is identified with the intellect of the individual and can be measured using the IQ.

Scientists who study the intellectual abilities of the individual claim that a high level of intelligence development implies a high level of creativity development. In the personal aspect, creativity is a feature of a creatively gifted person associated with the creation of new material and ideal products. For representatives of this direction, the fundamental point is the study of the personal characteristics of creative people, as a result of which their generalized personal portrait is created. In this regard, in the studies of E.E. Podguzova we find the following criteria of creativity [17]. 1. Non-standard. There is an unjustified shift in the meaning of concepts: the ability to create is identified with non-standard, in turn, with originality. Non-standard is a broader concept than the concept of originality. 2. Meaningfulness. The more the result corresponds to this criterion, the more creative it is. 3. Product value: the product must make a vivid impression and be generalizable, economical, cause irreversible changes in human experience, contain unusual sensory images or transformations, be valued or used by society or representatives of the sphere in which it was created.

The development of creativity throughout a person's life is uneven. Ivanchikhin V.G., S.M. Shurukht et al. believe that the sensitive period for the development of creativity is the age from 5 to 15 years [18, 68]. V.N. Druzhini and N.A. Khazratova, who believe that creativity is formed on the basis of general giftedness (as well as intelligence), distinguish at least two phases of creativity development. The first phase, which occurs at 3-5 years of age, is the development of "primary" creativity as a general creative ability, not specialized in relation to a certain area of human activity. At this time, the child's imitation of a significant adult as a creative model is possibly the main mechanism for the formation of creativity.

It is also possible that for some period creativity goes into a latent state (the phenomenon of "children's creativity"). The second phase is associated with adolescence and youth (from 13 to 20 years). During this period, "specialized" creativity is formed on the basis of "primary" creativity: the ability to create, associated with a certain sphere of human activity as its "reverse side", addition and alternative. At this stage, a special, significant role is played by a "professional" model, support from family and peers. The second phase ends with the denial of one's own imitative products and a negative attitude towards the former "ideal". The individual either lingers in the imitation phase forever, or moves on to original creativity [18].

V.S. Yurkevich suggests distinguishing "naive" creativity as the natural creative activity of preschool children, not associated with overcoming stereotypes, and "cultural" creativity, which is the result of their cognitive and personal development. The disappearance of "naive" creativity explains the fact of the decline in children's creative activity in elementary school. According to

the data obtained, this decline may be observed earlier in especially intellectually gifted children, so their creativity indicators at a certain stage may be lower than those of their ordinary peers. However, under conditions of stimulation of creative development, a high level of intelligence contributes to the more rapid development of "cultural" creativity, as a result of which the indicators of gifted children begin to outpace the indicators of other children [8].

Researchers of creativity development in ontogenesis agree that the age from 5 years is especially sensitive to the development of this quality, and the age stage following it - primary school age, has untapped potential and requires the creation of an environment that develops children's creativity. Summarizing the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature, we note that the concept of "creativity" implies not only and not so much a special mental process, as the result of a specifically organized perception, processing and reproduction of various aspects of objective reality. The concept of "creativity" is more oriented towards the personality, being a condition for creative self-development of the personality, as well as a significant reserve for its self-actualization, which can manifest itself in thinking, feelings, communication, individual types of activity, characterize the personality as a whole and / or its individual aspects, products of activity, the process of their creation. The structure of creativity can be represented by components that act simultaneously as stages of development of the ability to create in childhood, and an important characteristic is the observance of the conditions for the development of creativity of the individual. Primary school age is considered as a sensitive period for the development of creativity and creative activity of the individual, since the child at this age is active and inquisitive by nature, and the environment can be saturated with factors that develop creativity.

REFERENCES

1. Andreev, V. I. Dialectics of education and self-education of a creative personality: the basics of pedagogy and creativity [Text] / V. I. Andreev. - Kazan: Publishing house of Kazan University, 1988. - 238 p.
1. 2.Bashina T. F. Creativity as the basis of innovative pedagogical activity [Electronic resource] / T. F. Bashina // Young scientist. - 2013. - No. 53. - P. 81-85. - URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/51/6639/> (date of access: 08.10.2018).
2. The Great Soviet Encyclopedia [Text]: in 30 volumes / edited by A. M. Prokhorov. - M.: Soviet encyclopedia, 1974. - Vol. 16. - 631 p.
3. The Great Psychological Dictionary [Text] / compiled by B. G. Meshcheryakov, V. P. Zinchenko. - St. Petersburg: Prime-EVROZNAK: OLMA-PRESS, 2009. - 859 p.
4. Granovskaya, R. M. Creativity and Overcoming Stereotypes [Text] / R. M. Granovskaya, Yu. S. Krizhanskaya. - St. Petersburg: Imaton, 1994. - 239 p.
5. Druzhinin V. N. Activity, imitation, creativity [Electronic resource] / V. N. Druzhinin // School psychologist: appendix to the newspaper. "First September". - 2001. - No. 14. - URL: <http://psy.1september.ru/-article.php?ID=200101406> (date of access: 02.05.2018).
6. Erimbetova, S. Use of interactive (dialogue) teaching technologies in the process of creative self-development of students [Text] / S. Erimbetova, A. Madzhuga, B. Akhmetzhan // Bulletin of the Higher School. - 2003. - No. 11. - P. 48.
7. Ivanchikhin V. G. Formation of creativity of a schoolchild's personality [Electronic resource] / V. G. Ivanchikhin // Young scientist. - 2009. - No. 4. - P. 259-263. - URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/4/215/> (date of access: 11.03.2018).

8. Kodzhaspirova, G. M. Pedagogy [Text]: textbook. for university students / G. M. Kodzhaspirova. - M.: KNORUS, 2004. - 273 p.
9. Kolesina K. Yu. Development of creative abilities of students based on innovative technologies of teaching a foreign language [Electronic resource] / K. Yu. Kolesina. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article-/n/razvitie-kreativnyh-sposobnostey-obuchayuschih-sya-na-osnove-innovatsionnyh-tehnologiy-obucheniya-inostrannomu-yazyku> (date of access: 25.07.2018).
10. Kondratieva N. V. The essence of the concept of "creative abilities" [Electronic resource] / N. V. Kondratieva // Concept. - 2015. - No.: 9. - P. 106-110. - URL: <http://e-koncept.ru/2015/15320.htm> (date of access: 06.03.2018)
11. Krivenko, N. V. Independent work as a means of developing creative abilities of college students: (on the example of studying the humanitarian disciplines) [Text]: author's abstract. dis. ... candidate of ped. sciences: 13.00.08 / N. V. Krivenko; Surgut. state University. - Surgut, 2008. - 31 p.
12. Primary school of the XXI century [Electronic resource]: example. basics. educational program of primary general education. – URL: <https://shkolaveka.ru> (date of access: 15.10.2018).
13. Nietzsche, F. Beyond Good and Evil [Text] / F. Nietzsche. – M.: Azbuka-classic, 1999. – 416 p.
14. Sirotkin L. Yu. Creativity and creativity: possibilities of conceptual compromise [Electronic resource] / L. Yu. Sirotkin. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/tvorchestvo-i-kreativnost-vozmozhnosti-ponyatiynogo-kompromissa> (access date: 03/10/2018).
15. Slastenin, V. A. Pedagogy [Text]: textbook. manual for universities / V. A. Slastenin, I. F. Isaev, E. N. Shiyanov; edited by V. A. Slastenina. – M.: Academy, 2007. – 576 p.
16. Modern psychological dictionary [Text] / rep. ed. B. G. Meshcheryakov, V. P. Zinchenko. – M.: AST; SPb.: Prime-EVROZNAK, 2007. – 490 p.
17. Trubetskaya A. A. Application of innovative technologies in educational [Electronic resource] / A. A. Trubetskaya. – URL: http://baraninski_dnz.klasna.com/uk/article/primenenie-innovatsionnikh-tehnologii-v-vospitat.html (date of access: 29.03.2018).
18. Tsvirko N. A. Identification of musical creativity in primary school students [Electronic resource] / N. A. Tsvirko. – URL: <https://studfiles.net/preview/5358031/page:3/> (date of access: 03/29/2018).
19. <https://studfiles.net/preview/5358031/page:3/> (date of access: 03/29/2018).
20. Shurukht, S. M. Adolescence: development of creativity, self-awareness, emotions, communication and responsibility [Text] / S. M. Shurukht. – St. Petersburg: Rech, 2006. – 112 p.